

SBTBlogCert: A hybrid distributed data framework for blockchain-based recognition of academic weblogsUdsanee Pakdeetrakulwong^a, Suksawat Saelim^{b*}, Worachet Uttha^a and Dedy Syamsuar^c^aSoftware Engineering Department, Nakhon Pathom Rajabhat University, Nakhon Pathom, 73000, Thailand^bInformation Technology Department, Nakhon Pathom Rajabhat University, Nakhon Pathom, 73000, Thailand^cInformation Systems Department, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, 11480, Indonesia**CHRONICLE**

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ABSTRACT

User-generated content in academic weblog platforms fosters collaborative learning and knowledge dissemination. However, traditional weblog systems often lack transparent and verifiable mechanisms for recognising contributors, which limits the credibility of acknowledgement processes and the ability to provide authors with immutable proof of their accomplishments. In this paper, SBTBlogCert, a hybrid distributed data management framework that integrates centralised and decentralised infrastructures to acknowledge academic weblogs' user-generated content contributors, is introduced. For traditional Web 2.0 blog content management, a Supabase and PostgreSQL database is used. For Web 3.0 technologies, such as blockchain networks, Soulbound Tokens (SBTs), and the InterPlanetary File System (IPFS), are used to make sure that contributions are recognized in a transparent and decentralised way. A proof-of-concept prototype is designed and developed to evaluate the effectiveness of the hybrid distributed data management solution. This included performance metrics for web and blockchain, such as transaction latency, gas consumption, and transaction fees across multi-chain deployments. The results contribute to ongoing research in data and network science, especially in improving hybrid architectures that combine Web 2.0 cloud databases with Web 3.0 decentralised storage and verification networks.

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1. Introduction

User-generated content has become important in the digital economy because it can enhance growth and engagement across platforms, including social media networks, collaborative forums, and academic weblogs. However, content creators engage without contractual obligations, so they do not have motivation to contribute their work, resulting in a lack of user engagement (Dunn, Jensen, & Ralston, 2021). Therefore, to address these problems, an effective mechanism that acknowledges contributors, particularly when their work generates significant engagement, is required. Several content platforms have established systems to identify and promote user involvement (He, Luo, Tang, Wu, & Zhang, 2023). However, the main problem is the centralised nature of current content recognition, which raises concerns about contributors' long-term transparency and recognition. Blockchain and Non-fungible tokens (NFTs) are used in several blockchain projects. The reason is to create digital ownership of content. However, NFTs are less suitable for acknowledging individual accomplishments because they do not establish a connection to the original content creator. Therefore, in order to tackle this challenge, Soulbound Tokens (SBTs), first proposed by Ohlhaber, Weyl, and Buterin (2022), have been introduced as a non-transferable alternative to NFTs. SBTs cannot be transferred to others, which makes them well-suited for recognising personal accomplishments. In this paper, SBTBlogCert, a hybrid distributed data management framework that integrates centralised and decentralised infrastructures to acknowledge academic weblogs' user-generated content contributors, is introduced. For traditional Web 2.0 blog content management, a Supabase and PostgreSQL database is used. For Web 3.0 technologies, such as blockchain networks, Soulbound Tokens (SBTs), and the InterPlanetary File System (IPFS), are used to make sure that

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contributions are recognized in a transparent and decentralised way. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- It introduces a hybrid distributed data framework, integrating a centralised Web 2.0 component with decentralised Web 3.0 infrastructure in order to demonstrate interoperability and data synchronization across heterogeneous distributed file systems and databases.
- It proposes a distributed certificate management model, assuring tamper-resistant, verifiable, and cost-efficient record keeping while maintaining cross-layer data consistency between on-chain and off-chain components by leveraging SBTs and IPFS off-chain storage.
- It presents a multi-chain experimental evaluation conducted on the Sepolia, Avalanche C-Chain, and Polygon PoS networks to measure transaction latency and cost efficiency.

The remainder of this paper is arranged as follows. Section 2 presents background and related work. Section 3 explains the research methodology. Section 4 presents a blockchain-enabled recognition system for academic weblogs, while Section 5 is dedicated to the experimental evaluation. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 6 along with a discussion of work that might be conducted in the future.

2. Background and related work

The general concept of user-generated content and weblog applications is discussed in this section, along with an explanation of the problems involved in recognising creator contributions, and the potential of blockchain and SBTs to address these concerns.

2.1 User-generated content and weblog applications

User-generated content is a term used to describe the digital material, including text, images, or videos, which is created by the users of a platform (Santos, 2022). Platforms consider such content to be valuable because it ensures engagement, drives participation, and is typically generated at a frequency which allows new content to be regularly offered. From an academic perspective, weblog applications which rely on user-generated content play important roles in enabling collaboration, and facilitating the sharing of ideas and knowledge, thereby supporting the activities of learners, educators, and also researchers (Zamiri & Esmaceli, 2024). Weblogs are today an increasingly widely-used form of social communication, and make an important contribution to technology-supported learning (Garcia, Moizer, Wilkins, & Haddoud, 2019). They differ from ordinary blogging platforms in their focus upon research, education, and peer-to-peer learning, and can prove highly effective in boosting the writing and critical-thinking skills of university students. However, although such weblogs are undoubtedly useful, students are often reluctant to directly engage with such platforms since they do not perceive the value to their future academic achievements (Quadir, Yang, & Chen, 2022; Yousef, Salah, & Makram, 2020). Accordingly, it is vital to develop a robust approach which can promote the production of interesting and valuable content capable of drawing the attention of a larger audience.

2.2 The use of blockchain in recognising and incentivising user-generated content

Blockchain is a technological innovation which reduces the threat of fraud through the creation of a secure and transparent transaction ledger, allowing access to transaction records to all participants while ensuring that the record cannot be altered or manipulated (Singh et al., 2024). As a result, blockchain has found application in identifying and rewarding the creators of user-generated content which allows such content to be recognised and incentivised (Khobzi, Canhoto, & Ramezani, 2025). Research into this phenomenon can be classified either as incentivisation which makes use of monetisation, and incentivisation which does not. There is interest in blockchain-based monetisation since it can deliver an efficient and secure stream of revenue for content creators (Aldweesh, 2024). A system designed to promote the creation of user-generated content in the grocery sector via customer reviews online was proposed by Bruno et al. (2024). This platform was known as Re-Taled, and offered a transparent ecosystem in which user-generated content could be trusted, and users received tokens which gave access to prizes or discounts as rewards. In other work, Soares and Araújo (2024) employed blockchain alongside smart contracts to facilitate transparent payments while managing audiences on video streaming platforms, thus confirming that the use of blockchain-based architecture is indeed feasible. Moreover, the cost effectiveness of transactions made in this manner is also clearly demonstrated in the context of video streaming platforms. Blockchain-based platforms also featured in the work of Subramanian and Rouxelin (2024), whose investigation shed light upon the effects of cryptocurrency rewards and token prices as a means to encourage content creation by platform users. One case study on the Steemit platform revealed the need for reward mechanisms to ensure user engagement over the longer term, since this is a prerequisite for platform sustainability. Educational research has previously ventured into the study of blockchain usage for the purpose of recognising and incentivising those students who can produce valuable user-generated content. For instance, Ayman et al. (2023) focused on BlockCampus, a decentralised project whereby an online community was developed with the aim of fostering increased student involvement, so that connections and information could be shared among individuals whose interests aligned. The students who participated through comments or upvotes were given tokens as rewards. The ability of blockchain to enable a recognition system based on tokens in an academic context was also examined by Lee, Moroso, and Mackey (2023).

Furthermore, the use of blockchain might also be extended to the question of issuing and verifying degree certificates and other academic credentials (Al Hemaury et al., 2024; El Koshiry, Eliwa, Abd El-Hafeez, & Shams, 2023; Ramasamy & Khan, 2024; Rani, Sachan, & Kukreja, 2024). Blockchain is already widely employed in managing digital credentials and reward tokens, but is yet to be effectively applied in the creation of a unified, verifiable, and non-transferable system which might serve in this context for academic weblogs. Reward tokens have been shown to work in promoting participation, but they are transferable, and hence lack credibility in the academic setting. In addition, those systems which can be used successfully to verify formal academic credentials so not work so effectively in recognising the informal sector contributions which arise in educational blogging. The use of SBTBlogCert proposed in this paper offers a means to integrate both verification and recognition, through a system which issues verifiable and non-transferable certificates to participating students who generate valuable weblog content.

3. Research methodology

This study makes use of a design research framework initially proposed by Blessing and Chakrabarti (2009), which comprises four stages, namely criteria definition, descriptive study I, prescriptive study, and descriptive study II.

3.1 Criteria Definition

In this stage, the problem is identified and the objectives of the research are specified. In this case, the study focuses upon the problems associated with the maintenance of consistency, verifiability, and interoperability through a variety of data environments. The principal aim is to produce a hybrid distributed data architecture which is able to take a centralised relational database and combine it with decentralised storage and blockchain layers so that user-generated content can be reliably recognised. To achieve these goals, it will first be necessary to address several critical sub-objectives, which are discussed below.

- To introduce a distributed data framework for verified contributor acknowledgment by combining a centralized Web 2.0 database (Supabase/PostgreSQL) with decentralized file systems (IPFS) and blockchain networks.
- To implement mechanisms for cross-layer data synchronization and verifiable certificate management using SBTs to maintain integrity between on-chain and off-chain components.
- To assess the proposed solution by using a proof-of-concept prototype that measures key system performance indicators, including latency, cost-efficiency, and responsiveness across multiple blockchain networks.

3.2 Descriptive Study I

This step demands the investigation of existing systems to acquire insights which can shape the subsequent design of the hybrid distributed data solution. SBTs are shown to offer both security and non-transferability (Chen et al., 2023). To deliver data integrity, trust, interoperability, and operational efficiency, the hybrid model should integrate a centralised database with decentralised storage and blockchain verification. Such a solution would be effective across distributed environments.

3.3 Prescriptive Study: Design and Development

The prescriptive study stage emphasises designing and developing the intended solution with guidance from the previous stage. The system performs content management and controls user profiles through a typical Web 2.0 web-based infrastructure which also permits the tracking of user upvotes. This infrastructure is scalable because it is centralised, so it is cost-effective and able to manage substantial weblog interaction volumes without the problem of increasing operational costs. Non-transferable SBT token certificates can be issued for content creators upon receipt of enough upvotes, thus creating a permanent record of digital content ownership.

3.4 Descriptive Study II

In this last step, a proof-of-concept system prototype is tested to evaluate the overall framework. The three previously discussed blockchain networks (Sepolia, Avalanche C-Chain, and Polygon PoS) were employed in analysing and comparing transaction latency, gas usage, transaction fees, and general responsiveness.

4. SBTBlogCert: A Blockchain-Enabled Recognition System for Academic Weblogs

Combining Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 technologies, SBTBlogCert is a hybrid distributed data architecture framework which is able to issue SBT certificates, which serve as a verifiable and non-transferable form of recognition for individuals who contribute user-generated content to academic weblogs. The ecosystem defines three principal roles: general users, members, and moderators. General users are visitors who are able to read blog posts and have certificates verified, but are not registered. Members, however, are registered users, with the right to publish content, upvote content, and receive SBT certificates. Finally, moderators verify the published content, validate claims for certification, and can revoke that certification if a problem is discovered.

4.1 System design

The system design incorporates a number of key features as shown below:

1) User Management

This system delivers security in registration and authentication, while users have personalised profiles through which they are able to conveniently manage their accounts.

2) Content Management

Through the platform, members are able to create and publish content. To maintain the integrity of the work they produce, they are also able to report issues of plagiarism

3) Community interaction

Platform engagement is achieved through the ability of members to upvote content they find useful. These upvotes can then be counted to act as a measure of engagement, thus recognising those creators when their content attracts a predetermined number of votes.

4) Certificate Management

SBT certificates can be issued by SBTBlogCert at the point when an article achieves a predetermined level of upvote recognition. Certificates could also be revoked by platform moderators if it were necessary to do so, such as in cases involving plagiarism or other forms of content violation.

4.2 System Architecture and Implementation

The SBTBlogCert system architecture involves a structure comprising four layers, which are illustrated in Fig. 1 and can be described as follows:

Fig. 1. The SBTBlogCert architecture

1) Frontend Layer

User interactions are managed through the frontend layer, which enables communication between layers through REST API calls and JSON-RPC. This study makes use of Next.js to construct the user interface, while integration with the Web3 MetaMask wallet permits blockchain transactions.

2) Backend Layer

The backend layer is developed by Supabase, which also manages CRUD operations controlling the content of articles, user profiles, and the tracking of upvotes. User authentication is managed through OAuth, including MetaMask, GitHub, and Google.

3) Blockchain Layer

A smart contract written using Solidity is then deployed for testing using the three blockchain networks. Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) compatibility is demonstrated by each of the Sepolia test network and the Polygon Proof-of-Stake and Avalanche C-Chain mainnets. Automation of the SBT certificate issuance allows the process to be triggered as soon as a target level of engagement, measured in upvotes, is achieved. The other functions of the blockchain layer in this context include the verification, and, if necessary, revocation of certificates.

4) Data Layer

A hybrid data storage framework enables the storage of Web 2.0 components including article content, user data, and upvotes in the cloud-hosted Supabase/PostgreSQL. The various Web 3.0 components such as certificate metadata and images are then stored off-chain. This architecture makes use of IPFS as a peer-to-peer distributed file system. By using decentralised and relational databases, it becomes feasible in practice to manage interoperable distributed data systems.

4.3 SBTs certificate management module

The certificate management module is a key component of the SBTBlogCert framework and for evaluation purposes it is deployed for testing on three principal blockchain networks. The first is Sepolia, which is an official Ethereum testnet that lets smart contracts undergo testing at reasonable cost, while simulating the typical mainnet environment. The second is the Avalanche C-Chain, which is an EVM-compatible smart contract chain that employs the Snowman consensus protocol in the Avalanche Layer 1 blockchain platform. Finally, the third is Polygon PoS, which is an EVM-compatible sidechain that delivers a Layer 2 scaling solution secured by a Proof-of-Stake mechanism. It undergoes optimisation so that transactions will be both quick and cheap. The certificate-related modules have the critical role of controlling the issuance, verification, and revocation of certificates. An outline of the relevant mechanisms follows.

4.3.1 Certificate issuance

SBT issuance occurs upon the number of upvotes for a given article reaching a predetermined number. The system duly issues a certificate of recognition on the chosen blockchain network (Sepolia, Avalanche C-Chain, or Polygon PoS). Certificate metadata can be stored on IPFS as a JSON file, while its content identifier (CID) is embedded within the SBT. A smart contract built on the OpenZeppelin ERC721 standard can customize transfer-related functions to guarantee SBT non-transferability. The structure of the SBT certificate metadata is explained below:

$$T_x = \{Name_{cert}, Title_{cert}, Name_{blog}, Name_{auth}, Desc_{cert}, IPFS_{hash}\}$$

Where

$Name_{cert}$: The certificate name.

$Title_{cert}$: The certificate type or title.

$Name_{blog}$: The blog or article title for which the certificate is awarded.

$Name_{auth}$: The certificate recipient's name.

$Desc_{cert}$: A short description of the achievement for awarding the certificate.

$IPFS_{hash}$: IPFS Hash which links to the certificate's image.

One example of a JSON object which represents the metadata is shown as:

```
{
  "name": "Certificate's Blockchain Technology: A Revolution in Data Transparency",
  "title": "Certificate of Merit for Engaging Content",
  "blogName": "Blockchain Technology: A Revolution in Data Transparency",
  "author": "Wipa Saelim",
  "description": "Certificate for 100 upvotes on Blockchain Technology: A Revolution in Data Transparency blog",
  "image": "ipfs://QmWhrNBmdjVgVFmvwT9oZywLgMSuXGzs7EJ8fFp8x7Zhd8"
}
```

Fig. 2 illustrates the flowchart diagram depicting how the SBTBlogCert smart contract is implemented to issue certificates (mintCertificate function).

Fig. 2. Certificate issuance process flowchart

When the upvotes for an article reach a predetermined number, the process of certificate minting begins automatically. Members are then able to use the frontend interface to request the SBT certificate. This request triggers the appearance of a MetaMask wallet prompt, allowing the member to verify their identity and sign the transaction, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Minting a certificate with MetaMask confirmation

The signed transaction can then be transferred to the smart contract, which executes the minting of an SBT certificate with permanent links to the wallet of the member. Decentralisation is guaranteed by the storage of metadata on IPFS. When completed, transactions are stored on the blockchain, while members have the benefit of a certificate which can be independently verified through the system, as Fig. 4 illustrates.

Fig. 4. Blockchain storage of the minted certificate which is connected to IPFS for verification

The minted SBT certificate appears in Fig. 4. Important information including the token URI, token ID, date of issue, and owner address can be observed, along with key metadata such as the name of the certificate, the type of certificate, the blog name, author name, and image of the IPFS certificate.

4.3.2 Certificate verification

It is possible for visitors or third parties, with LinkedIn serving as an example, to have certificates verified via the system even if the visitor is unaware of the details or procedures associated with the blockchain technology. Two important aspects of this system can be presented as integrity and authenticity. To exhibit integrity, the certificate metadata must not be susceptible to tampering or unauthorised alteration. The verification of IPFS hashes with the stored blockchain data achieves this goal. To exhibit authenticity, the certificate origins must be linked to an authorised entity, matching the blockchain data. Fig. 5 presents a verification certificate; to confirm the certificate authenticity, the platform verification process involves the matching of user data to the blockchain record.

Fig. 5. Certificate verification result

In addition, the system promotes wider recognition via granting permission for certificates to be shared through a range of professional platforms. This is accomplished by generating public verification links, as shown in Fig. 6. When users access a credential, the result of the certificate verification is shown directly by the SBTBlogCert platform, as illustrated in Figure 7. The Token ID is automatically acquired from the URL and the related certificate metadata so that on-chain verification can be carried out with no need for any input from the user. Users are also able to verify their credentials independently by using public blockchain explorers. Sepolia Etherscan for Sepolia, SnowTrace for Avalanche C-Chain, and Polygonscan for the Polygon PoS chain can be used for this purpose, allowing the authenticity of certificates to be checked independently of the proposed platform. Decentralised verification therefore increases trust and transparency.

Licenses & certifications

Fig. 6. 'Show Credential' on LinkedIn is connected to SBTBlogCert

Fig. 7. Result of certificate verification

4.3.3 Certificate revocation

Certification integrity is maintained through an approach which permits certificate revocation if a moderator detects a problem. Fig. 8 shows the interface used by the moderator when viewing certificates which are identified by a Token ID and IPFS hash. If the moderator chooses to have a certificate revoked, a MetaMask panel is opened within the system which allows the moderator either to accept or reject transactions.

Fig. 8. Moderator interface allowing revocation of certificates

5. Experimental Evaluation

The research design required evaluation of the proposed solution by use-case simulations involving a proof-of-concept system prototype. This assessment placed emphasis upon the performance of the web application which manages the web content, and the blockchain infrastructure which manages the issuance of certificates. This evaluation was carried out within a controlled laboratory environment to achieve both reliability and accuracy. The experimental setup made use of Windows 11 with an Intel Core i7-1165G7 processor and 16 GB of RAM.

5.1 Web application performance metrics

Web performance testing was carried out using Google Lighthouse, which has found popular use in research and software development (Heričko, Šumak, & Brdnik, 2021). The findings can be seen in Fig. 9.

The developed system exhibited outstanding metrics for web performance, achieving a score of 100. The indicators of First Contentful Paint and Largest Contentful Paint, measuring 0.3 and 0.4 seconds respectively, were used to indicate the speed of user interactions with the platform. The indicator of user experience, Total Blocking Time, was strong at 20 milliseconds, while a value of zero was recorded for the Cumulative Layout Shift. Interactions were accordingly seamless, while the stability of the visual presentation was ensured.

Fig. 9. Web performance evaluation results from Google Lighthouse

5.2 Blockchain evaluation

To measure the blockchain performance within the developed framework, the principal factors of transaction latency and gas-related costs, along with transaction fees and gas usage are examined. Transaction latency is widely investigated in this context because it represents an excellent indicator of system performance from the perspective of the user (Fan, Ghaemi, Khazaei, & Musilek, 2020). The cost component of the system is also significant, however, as it is necessary to minimise the transaction fees and gas usage to ensure that the application operates in a cost-effective manner. The suitability of the different blockchain networks in issuing SBT certificates was then assessed. The three networks comprised Avalanche C-Chain (a Layer 1 blockchain solution), Polygon PoS (an Ethereum-compatible Layer 2 solution), and Sepolia (Ethereum's testnet). In terms of cost advantage, it makes Sepolia become the better choice instead of the Ethereum mainnet. The Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM), EIP-1559 transaction fee model, and Proof-of-Stake consensus mechanism are all the same for both the Ethereum mainnet and Sepolia testnet, so evaluation of the Sepolia testnet offers results which are similar to those which would arise when evaluating the Ethereum mainnet, confirming the suitability of Sepolia as a proxy when investigating performance for mainnet deployment. The evaluation was carried out in the period from November 2024 to February 2025, using Hardhat, a popular development environment facilitating automated deployment, testing, and accurate transaction measurements over different networks.

5.2.1 Measuring Transaction Latency

The time taken from submitting to confirming a transaction on the blockchain is known as latency. It indicates the usability and efficiency of blockchain applications (Alharby & Management, 2023). When the user experience is responsive, latency is typically low, and this can be considered highly desirable when academic certificates are to be issued. Transaction latency is calculated using Eq. (1):

$$\text{Transaction Latency} = T_2 - T_1 \quad (1)$$

In which: T_1 = Time for transaction submission

T_2 = Time for transaction confirmation

Average transaction latency can be calculated using the formula shown as Eq. (2):

$$\text{Average Latency} = (1/n) * \Sigma(L_i) \quad (2)$$

In which: n = Number of transactions to mint certificates

L_i = Transaction latency of the i -th transaction to mint certificates.

5.2.2 Gas Consumption and Transaction Fee

The gas consumption of the smart contract function was analysed in order to measure the overall cost efficiency, although it is important to consider that gas fees are applicable solely to those functions which actually change the state of the blockchain; there are no gas costs associated with read-only functions, and such functions are not contributors to latency (Truong, Le, & Le, 2024). Calculation of the transaction fee makes use of the formula shown below as Eq. (3) (Masla, Vyas, Gautam, Shaw, & Ghosh, 2021):

$$\text{Transaction Fee} = \text{Gas Used} \times \text{Gas Price} \quad (3)$$

The different blockchain networks used in this study all maintained the same gas usage levels in this study, due to IPFS storing the certificate metadata off-chain in the form of a fixed-length content identifier. Employing IPFS for storage lowers the on-chain data size and in turn reduces gas costs, enhancing efficiency. Crucially, it should be noted that this assessment only considers the process of SBT certificate issuance. The findings are listed in Table 1, which shows the analysis of transaction latency, gas consumption, and transaction fees when certificates are issued using the three blockchain networks of Sepolia, Avalanche C-Chain, and Polygon PoS. The confirmation times, in order of speed, were 2.02 seconds (Avalanche C-Chain), 4.31 seconds (Polygon PoS), and 8.80 seconds (Sepolia).

Table 1

Analysis of the transaction latency and gas usage associated with SBT certificate issuance

Blockchain	Average Transaction Latency (sec)	Average Gas Used (units)	Average Transaction Fee	Average Transaction Fee (USD)
Sepolia (Ethereum)	8.80	152,922	0.006922777769229168 ETH	\$18.19
Avalanche C-Chain	2.02	152,922	0.000305844000305844 AVAX	\$0.007387
Polygon PoS	4.31	152,922	0.009317805991949532 POL	\$0.002543

Note: On 8 February 2025, ETH in USD = \$2,627.558, AVAX in USD = \$24.15, and POL in USD = \$0.273

In Fig. 10, a comparison between average gas usage and average transaction fees is presented, with a logarithmic scale employed to better reflect the differences in cost.

Fig. 10. Comparison of gas usage and transaction fees associated with SBT certificate issuance

Fig. 10 reveals that under constant gas usage at 152,922 units as a result of IPFS, the different networks had different transaction fees as a consequence of the unique algorithms they employ for gas pricing. The single transaction costs were \$0.002543 (Polygon PoS), \$0.007387 (Avalanche C-Chain), and \$18.19 (Sepolia).

5.3 Discussion and Practical Concerns

Within the context of distributed blockchain environments, the current study compares outcomes for latency, cost efficiency, and decentralisation. Transaction latency was at its lowest for Avalanche C-Chain, so this blockchain should be well-suited for real-time certificate issuance. Overall, the performance of Polygon PoS was the most economical, underlining its applicability for scenarios of large scale use or frequent transaction where efficiency is of greater importance than latency. The Ethereum mainnet, for which this study used Sepolia as a proxy, maximises security and decentralisation, so this option would be most suitable for high value certifications where trust is crucial, and where global integrity and permanence are necessary (Diaconita, Belciu, & Stoica, 2023). However, in cases where frequent issuance is necessary, high transaction fees and long confirmation times do not support its implementation. Since Sepolia serves as the official Ethereum testnet, it does however provide an affordable way of replicating mainnet performance as new systems are developed and require testing.

When considering distributed data, combining the blockchain with IPFS-based off-chain storage has the effect of lowering the on-chain data volume, so throughput is enhanced without adversely influencing verifiable data integrity. The hybrid distributed model is confirmed to be viable, as the centralised databases are able to manage structured data while the immutable verification records are handled by the decentralised networks. It is therefore clear that SBTBlogCert achieves a suitable balance between cost, trust, and performance when appropriately deployed through heterogeneous blockchain networks. The findings reveal helpful insights concerning distributed data and network science, especially for the optimisation of blockchain-based architectures in the context of verifiable data management applications where latency and costs are critical factors.

6. Conclusion and Future Recommendations

This study presents SBTBlogCert, which is a hybrid, distributed data management platform making use of a centralised relational database with integrated decentralised file systems and blockchain technology. It offers a means to recognise academic weblog content creator contributions in a verifiable and transparent manner. Through the application of PostgreSQL, IPFS, and multi-chain blockchain networks (Avalanche C-Chain, Polygon PoS, and Ethereum Sepolia), it can be confirmed that a combination of different data layer types serves to guarantee data consistency and traceability while simultaneously creating a secure distributed environment which avoids susceptibility to tampering.

In the future, lightweight consensus algorithms or layer-2 rollups might be investigated with the aim of lowering both latency and gas costs from current levels. Exploration of the feasibility of framework expansion to multi-agent and decentralised identity systems may be beneficial in permitting broader applicability across a range of distributed ecosystems, covering elements such as academic credentialing, the management of digital reputations, and data sharing in a secure and reliable manner.

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